

**SOME LEGAL ASPECTS OF ENGLISH LAW PERTAIN TO THE ESTABLISHMENT OF
CONTRACTS FOR LINER SHIPPING CARRIAGES BY SEA**

Kostadinov O.D.

*Ph.D., Guest lecturer of the Department
"Operation and Management of Merchant fleet"*

*Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy
Varna, Bulgaria*

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9183-5243

Abstract

The most characteristic feature and difference between contractual relations in liner shipping and tramp shipping, as well as other contracts for the provision of maritime transport services, is the formation of contractual relations in liner shipping. In liner shipping, the negotiation of the terms of carriage and the actual formation of the contract of carriage take place in two stages. In the first stage, the carrier makes an offer for transportation, which includes the general conditions of transportation and the freight, which is according to the tariff. These conditions are the same for all consignors and are not subject to renegotiation. If the shippers agree, they confirm the offer, after which the carrier prepares and sends a booking note to the shipper. A booking note is only a contract to reserve a place on the ship for the carriage of the specified cargo. After the goods are loaded, a bill of lading is issued with the terms of carriage included, which is considered proof of a concluded contract.

Keywords: liner carriage; booking note; liner bill of lading; general conditions for liner carriage; common tariff; contract formation in liner shipping.

Study in Support of Maritime Commercial Practice

1. Introduction to Liner Shipping

Definition of Liner Shipping: Liner shipping is an organization for carrying out sea transports, which are carried out in a planned and continuous mode. In liner shipping, carriers carry out transportation between pre-announced ports on the respective line and according to the schedule. All consignors share the same transportation conditions, and a universal tariff determines their prices. The freight (carriage price) includes the cost of loading and unloading.

Liner shipping is regulated by Regulation (EC) No. 906/2009 of the European Commission dated September 28, 2009.

Definition of Liner Shipping: *"Liner Shipping" means the carriage of goods carried out regularly on one or more specified routes between ports and according to schedules and dates of voyages that are announced in advance, such carriage being available, even incidentally, to any user of transport for a fee.*[1]

Under English maritime private law, liner carriers are "common carriers", and the same operate under pre-announced general terms and conditions, the same for all consignors, and the price of the transports is according to the tariff valid for all. Generally, common carriers are required to transport all passengers and cargo until the vessel's capacity reaches its limit. Usually, shippers pay the carriage charges in advance, and carriers risk lawsuits for damages if they unreasonably refuse carriage. When transport occurs within the borders of a single country, that country regulates this activity.[2] The status of common carriers is governed by the Carriers Act 1830 (CA 1830).[3] In liner shipping, in each of the ports of the line, the ships are served by liner agents, whose second main function is to attract cargo for carriage (booking of cargo). Line agents are engaged in receiving and handing over the cargo on behalf

of the carrier, as well as organizing their transshipment work in the loading and unloading ports, because the conditions of transportation are linear - Liner-In / Liner-Out and it is the duty of the carriers.[4]

2. Liner Bill of Lading as per English Law

A liner bill of lading is used in traditional liner shipping. Contracts for carriage in liner shipping are settled (materialized) by signing a liner bill of lading. The shipowner owns and operates the ship, both technically and commercially. The shipowner can be the shipowner, the shipowner (bareboat charterer), or the time charterer can take over the commercial functions of the shipowner. The actual technical operation of the ship is carried out by the ship's crew and technical personnel ashore, who are appointed, directed, and controlled by the shipowner. The shipowner disposes of (operates) the ship and, at his own expense, carries out his own commercial activity, consisting in the transportation of foreign cargoes against the due freight. The actual commercial activity is carried out by the commercial department in the shipowner's office (chartering department) and the line agents (liner agents). In these contracts, the shipowner is responsible for loading and unloading the goods, i.e., trading on liner shipping terms (liner in/liner out terms). Fixed costs (daily running costs and capital costs) and variable costs (voyage expenses) of the ship are for the account of the shipowner. The consignor pays the shipowner the freight, including costs for the transshipment activities.

- Legal features: ownership of the ship is with the shipowner. The earning capacity of the ship is for the shipowner, or bareboat charterer, or time charterer, depending on whether the vessel sails on a bareboat and/or time charter.

- Organizational features: The ship carries out liner shipping, for which the carrier is the party with the right to use the earning capacity of the ship.

- Cargo responsibility: The cargo is the responsibility of the carrier under the bill of lading, who may be the shipowner or the charterers on the previous bareboat charter or time-charter chain. The name of the carrier shall be recorded on the bill of lading.

- Appendix: Liner bills of lading are evidence of a contract of carriage in liner shipping, with the terms of carriage included on the first page. The contractual process begins with booking (reserving) a place of carriage. It is done by signing a booking note, which, according to BIMCO, is a contract to reserve a place for the carriage of a specific commodity with a specific vessel sailing on a scheduled line. Among the acceptance of the goods, the ship owner (carrier) issues a Received Bill of Lading, and after loading it on board the ship, the Shipped Bill of Lading is reissued. The signed transport document (bill of lading or waybill) from the master or line agent is evidence of the contract for carriage of the goods, including the conditions of carriage.[5]

3. Formation of Liner shipping contracts

The formation of contracts in the traditional linear transportation of general cargo is by issue booking note and line bill of lading. Liner bill of lading, and liner waybill is characterized by the fact that the ships of one company sail according to a schedule between previously announced ports of the respective line. The conditions of carriage are general and publicly announced. Line carriers accept for carriage any offered cargo, provided that it is suitable for the ship, the carriage is between ports of the line, and the cargoes are accepted for carriage by the first passing ship with free space. For these reasons, liner carriers are also called common carriers. The negotiation process and formation of carriage contracts differ from those of other commercial shipping organizations in that the conditions of carriage are pre-announced by the carrier and cannot be changed. The reason for the pre-set conditions of the transports is that, in principle, with liner transports, many small lots are transported to different consignors, which makes it impossible to negotiate different conditions separately for each load with each of the consignors, which can be many. This is the rationale behind the simpler form used for negotiating the carriage of goods.

The formation of contractual relationships is carried out according to a certain technological process. The basis of this process is a tariff and general conditions of carriage that are valid for all consignors. Once the shipper has made an inquiry for carriage of a particular commodity between two or more ports of the line concerned, and provided the commodity is suitable for the carrier's ships, then the line agent sends the carriage offer. The carriage offer includes the name of the first ship that can accept the goods, the period in which the ship is expected to arrive at the port of loading, and the freight under the relevant tariff number, accompanied by the general conditions of carriage. If the consignor agrees to have his goods transported according to the liner agent's offer, the latter confirms. For the agreement reached, the line agents prepare the so-called Booking note „, Booking Note ", which is signed by both parties. According to the materials from the BIMCO library [<https://www.bimco.org/>], a Booking

Note is not a contract of carriage by sea, but only a contract of reserved place for the carriage of a specific commodity. Also, according to materials from the BIMCO library, judicial practice does not know cases of a claim against a consignor who has a confirmed "Booking Note", but did not secure the goods for carriage. It should be clarified here that this applies only to linear transports. It is a bad practice in tramp transportation to use similar and unconfirmed documents for this type of transportation. When using such a document in tramp shipping, it is logical to consider that a charter has been concluded, giving rise to the corresponding obligations for the charterer as well.[6]

4. Acceptance of the cargo and issuance of the transport documents

After receiving the goods, the line agent issues a temporary bill of lading (Received B/L) - valid until the goods are loaded.

Shipped B/L is issued by the carrier's shipping agent, which, in addition to the usual functions that bills of lading have, also contains the conditions of the contract of carriage.

In liner shipping, as well as in tramp shipping, the transport document, in addition to a bill of lading, can also be a Waybill (for maritime transport) or a Consignment Note (for inland waterways in Europe).

Shipping documents in liner shipping differ in content from those in tramp shipping. Line bills of lading and bills of lading also contain the conditions of carriage. In tramp shipping, the conditions of carriage are regulated by the concluded charter. In liner shipping, there is no concluded charter duly signed by both parties, but nevertheless contractual relations are considered to be formed with the issuance of the liner bill of lading or liner waybill. Figuratively speaking, the consignor with one hand hands over the relevant goods to the carrier, and with the other hand receives from the carrier the liner bill of lading or liner waybill for the same goods. It is important to note here that with the act of handing over and accepting the goods, the risk of loss or damage to the goods passes from the consignor to the consignee, who can seek liability from the carrier. The liner bill of lading and liner waybill can be considered not only as evidence of a concluded contract, but also as an official document including the terms of a contract of carriage. In this regard, there are two types of bills of lading. Bills of lading, which are issued pursuant to a concluded contract for sea carriage, or the so-called Charter Party Bill of Lading used in Tramp Shipping and Liner Bills of Lading, which are used in liner shipping. In the second type of transport documents, the terms of the contract are contained in the bill of lading, i.e. the terms of the contract are included in the bill of lading itself (the contract is contained in Bill of Lading). The last and current line bill of lading issued by BIMCO is CONLINEBILL 2000. In this connection, a line waybill LINEWAYBILL is also issued. The above trade practice applies to traditional liner shipping.

5. Analysis of the contractual process in combined linear transport with intermodal units

In addition to the traditional liner shipping, which is already of limited application, there are new practices

with the so-called combined liner shipping. In combined linear transport, the goods are loaded in intermodal units - containers, trucks or truck trailers, railway wagons, lighters and pallets. The operators of the intermodal units conclude the relevant transport contracts with the consignors and, after loading the goods, issue the transport document - bill of lading or waybill for the transportation of the goods along the entire route, along which, if there is a sea section, the intermodal unit with the goods loaded in it is reloaded and carried by the relevant type of seagoing vessel which, in principle, maintains a line between two or more ports. Example: container shipping. In these cases, the name of the ship is also noted on the transport document, when the intermodal unit is transhipped on board the ship, the master of the ship or the line agents sign the bill of lading as evidence that the intermodal unit with the goods has been accepted on board the ship. In this type of water transport, sea carriers are subcarriers of the major carriers, i.e. the operators of the intermodal units, in addition to the contract of carriage with the consignors, conclude another contract with the sea carrier as a subcontractor for the carriage of the cargo on the sea section of the route. The transportation of other types of intermodal units is organized in an identical way. Intermodal units are transported by container ships, Ro-Ro, rail ferries, lighter carriers (LASH) and pallet carriers, respectively. It is important to note that usually after the goods are loaded into the intermodal unit, the latter is sealed by customs at the place of loading, and unsealed by customs at the place of receipt of the goods. The intermodal carrier is responsible for the goods to its consignees. Sea carriers, as subcontractors, are responsible for the integrity of customs seals during sea transportation, as well as the protection of the intermodal unit from external influence and damage. In the event of damage to the transported goods by the sea carrier, the damage shall be settled between the sea carrier and the intermodal unit carrier, who in turn shall be liable to the consignee of the goods. Between the operators of the intermodal units and the sea carriers there may be a general contract of carriage, also voyage contracts – e.g. in Ro-Ro transports, when the goods are transported by motor vehicle, when the truck with the trailer is loaded on board the ship, sea freight is paid and the corresponding issued payment document is proof of a concluded contract, with valid general conditions of carriage of the sea carrier. Of the known combined liners, container liners are of greatest importance and future. Container operators have an established commercial network with line agents, they also have a

material base that is their property or taken on long-term lease. Large container operators use their own sea and river fleet, containers and trucks to transport the containers, including container terminals and depots.[7], [8]

6. Conclusion

In traditional liner shipping, consignors receive an offer with the general conditions of carriage as it is the same for all consignors, also freight according to a tariff valid for all consignors of the line. Consignors book (reserve) a place for their cargo if they accept the offer, against which the carrier issues a booking note as a reserved place contract. The contract for liner carriage is formed when the goods are handed over to the carrier, against which the consignor receives a liner bill of lading with the terms of carriage included in it. A liner bill of lading is not a contract for carriage, but only evidence of a concluded contract, which includes the terms of the contract for carriage itself. The contract for liner carriage is formed by the act of handing over the goods for loading and carriage against which the liner bill of lading is obtained.

References

1. COMMISSION REGULATION (EC) No:906/2009 of September 28, 2009
2. Definition of " common carrier", The Free Dictionary by Farlex, <https://legal.dictionary.thefreedictionary.com/common+carrier>
3. Carriers Act, 1830, <http://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1830/act/68/enacted/en/print.html>
4. Gordon, L., Ihre, R., Sandevam, A., Shipbroking and Chartering practice, 4th Edition, Lloyd's of London Press, The liner market, 1995, pp.5
5. Byung-Mun Lee and Jung-Ho Yang, The Bill of Lading Functioning as the Contract of Carriage in English Law, Journal of Korea Trade, Vol.10, No.2, August 2006, pp 169-186
6. Aikens, R. Lord, R., Bools, M., Bills of Lading 2nd Edition, informa law from Routledge, Definition and Classification of B/L, ISBN: 978-1-315-75087-3 (ebk), 2016
7. UNCTAD, UN, Contracts for the carriage of goods by sea and multimodal transport, UNCTAD/DTL/TLB/INF/2022/1
8. Zajac, M., Swieboda, J., Rastel, F., Analysis and evaluation of selected transport process in the inland intermodal terminal, The International Journal of TRANSPORT & LOGISTICS, ISSN 1451-107X, 2014